

THE ROLE OF IMPROVING HOUSEHOLD INCOME AND LIVING STANDARDS IN ECONOMIC GROWTH OF A COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the role of improving household income and living standards, analyzes 3 different Living Standards Components, clarifies and highlights the correlation of the three terms: household income, living standards and economic growth. The total income of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan of a certain period is also provided to simplify the main idea of the article.

Key words: household income, living standards, economic growth, living standards components, GDP, well-being, population.

INTRODUCTION

At present, the republic's economy based on market relations provides for the accelerated development of production by deepening reforms and modernizing the national economy, raising the standard of living of the population, in particular increasing the incomes of each household.

Standard of living is the level of wealth, comfort, material goods, and necessities available to an individual or socioeconomic class in a certain geographic area, usually

in country. The standard of living includes factors such as income, quality and availability of employment, class disparity, poverty rate, quality and affordability of housing, hours work required purchase necessities, gross domestic product, inflation rate, amount of leisure time every year, affordable (or free) access to quality healthcare, quality and availability of education, life expectancy, incidence of disease, cost of goods and services, infrastructure, national economic growth, economic and political stability, freedom, environmental quality, climate and safety. The standard of living is closely related to quality of life.

With the growth of the household incomes, the country also creates conditions for the effective use of these incomes, by developing its economy simultaneously, which are achieved, for instance, by localizing the production of consumer goods and increasing their production and expanding the types of services provided to the population.

METHODS

The type of research conducted in this article are qualitative as well as quantitative one. The secondary data (and primary data at some points) was collected to analyze and draw conclusion on a chosen topic.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESULTS

By analyzing different economic literatures, giving one-sided definitions to the terms “Economic Growth”, “Living Standards”, “Household Incomes” and “Well-Being of the Population” is quite unfair.

According to the economist Akrom Muminov, “Economic Growth” is an increase in the gross domestic product (GDP) and its value per capita¹⁶.

Economic growth means not only the growth of real income of a country, but also the growth of real income per capita. Economic growth is defined as a change in real GDP compared to the previous period and is used to determine the dynamics of the country's overall economic opportunities.

Economic growth of a certain country in a certain year is calculated by the formula provided in the table 1 and the results are obtained in percentages. In this case, the percentage growth of the current year's real GDP is compared to the base year (mainly the previous year), i.e.:

¹⁶ <https://mineconomy.uz/uz/info/1200>

Table 1. Economic growth formula

$$\text{Economic growth} = (\text{real GDP of the current year} / \text{real GDP of the base year}) * 100$$

Considering a number of scientific literature sources it could be concluded that the economic growth is an increase in total supply, or, in other words, an increase in real and potential GDP.

In the article “The ways of improvement of living standards” (by N.Muminov., T.Kim., and others) [1] living standards components are distinguished according to 3 different models and concept. In the table 2, living standard structures of UN, the Swedish as well as the French models are illustrated, where the human-being welfare is put at the central point of consideration.

As it can be noticed from the table 2, each model puts different aspects at the top place, that is, health; employment and working conditions; the size and composition of the population, labor resources and working conditions in UN concept, Swedish and French models respectively.

Table 2. Living Standards Components¹⁷

UN Concept	The Swedish model	French model
1. Health	1. Employment and working conditions	1. The size and composition of the population, labor resources and working conditions
2. Food Consumption	2. Economic Opportunities	2. Distribution and use of income
3. Education	3. Political opportunities	3. Activity conditions
4. Employment and working conditions	4. School education	4. Social aspects of living standards
5. Housing conditions	5. Health and medical care	
6. Social security	6. Social Opportunities	
7. Clothes	7. Housing	
8. Leisure and leisure time	8. Consumption	
9. Human rights	9. Free time and leisure	

¹⁷ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339847000_THE_WAYS_OF_IMPROVEMENT_OF_LIVING_STANDARDS

As for UN Concept of living standards, it tends to be similar to the Maslow's hierarchy of needs, ranging from basic needs to psychological ones, whereas the other two take mostly social, political and economic aspects into consideration.

All in all, there are several factors here to stay that are included within the term "living standards", that is, the term has a wide meaning that should be related multilaterally instead of approaching in a biased way.

The term "Well-Being" is also defined differently by different sources. According to A.Ulmasov and A.Vahobov [2], well-being means the quantity and quality of life benefits consumed by people, and the general conditions of living.

As for the term "Household Income", it is a measure of the combined income of all people living in a particular household or place of residence. It includes all types of income, such as salaries and wages, pension income, near-cash government transfers such as food stamps, and investment income.

According to The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan On Statistics [3], the total income of the population includes cash income and income in kind, consists of receipts, which, as a rule, have the property of repeatability and are received by the household or its individual members on a regular basis, annually or at shorter intervals.

To be more precise with the main notion and point of view highlighted in this article, let us analyze the income of the population of a certain country (of the Republic of Uzbekistan in our case).

Table 3¹⁸

Total income of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan
(preliminary data for January-March 2022)

¹⁸ <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/20902-total-income-of-the-population-january-march-2022>

The total income of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-March, in 2022, is given in the table 3. As it can be seen, real growth rate of total income accounted for 105.4% while that of per capita was 113.6%.

In the figure 1, the least total income per capita is in Namangan region with 2,330,600 sums, while Tashkent city is the region with the highest income level at the first quarter of 2022.

By summarizing the data in the table 3 and figure 1, it could be concluded that there were positive changes in terms of household income comparing previous periods.

Figure 1

Contribution of industries to GDP growth in January-June 2022 in the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁹:

A positive contribution to GDP growth was made by the sectors of agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 0.6 p.p. (in January-June 2021 - 0.4 p.p.), industry - 1.3 p.p. (in January-June 2021 - 2.2 p.p.), construction - 0.4 p.p. (in January-June 2021 - 0.1 p.p.) and services - 2.8 p.p. (in January-June 2021 - 3.9 p.p.). Due to the growth of net taxes on products, GDP increased by 0.3 percentage points. (in January-June 2021 - 0.6 p.p.).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Considering the statistics above, the correlation between households and a country's economic growth could be defined as follows. As a person makes households, households make societies, consequently, societies make countries. The higher the population and household income is, the higher the economic growth is. Countries with higher income level households tend to generate higher and higher tax bases, whose revenue could be used for increasing a number of public services such as healthcare, transport system, education and etc., which are one of the indicators of the well-being of the population.

When the households try to make incomes, they unconsciously contribute to the economic chain of a country's economy either by their labor or workforce or by creating intellectual properties, or at least by being the minor participants of this economic chain. In one words, the more there are attempts in making money from households, the more there are attempts in increasing the economy.

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¹⁹ <https://stat.uz/en/press-center/news-of-committee/26296-2022-yilning-yanvar-iyun-oylarida-yaim-o-sishida-tarmoqlarning-hissasi-3>

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